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AVENUE Project, safety assessment of automated minibuses

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Abstract

To gain relevance and therefore acceptance, automated minibuses require higher operating-speeds and ability to operate without on board safety drivers, on more flexible routes. This causes significant safety challenges, out of which the *Safety of the Intended Functionality* (SOTIF), i.e. the identification and mitigation of threats resulting from inadequacy between one vehicle's capacities and the conditions in which it is used, is the most stringent. Within this context, a methodology has been developed. It relies on various kinds of data collection to identify and characterise threats, and numerical simulations to extrapolate findings to new conditions. Following that methodology, a catalogue of safety-relevant scenarios has been constituted. Those scenarios have been prioritised using a ranking algorithm relying on hundreds of votes by public transport operators' employees operating automated minibus as part of the H2020 AVENUE project, and the most relevant ones characterised, using detailed sensor data. An injury risk study has built risk functions for both passengers and pedestrians in case, respectively, of harsh braking or collision. Finally, a simulation environment has been set-up, allowing virtual testing of an automated minibus model by staging aforementioned safety-relevant scenarios.

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Keywords:

Autonomous Transport, Safety

Context

Small and medium sized, shared automated vehicles (i.e. automated minibuses) seem like a promising way to address some public transport operators' issues, notably offering a service on low traffic/peripheral routes, where traditional busses would not be economically viable or not flexible enough.

AVENUE H2020 project aims at demonstrating the suitability and efficiency of small and medium automated minibuses for different transport models under development in Europe. Its goals are not only to assess such vehicles' safety in public transports, but also to demonstrate the economic, environmental and social advantages of automated vehicles for both the exploiting companies and the users, opening the way for their full scale adoption in public transport after the end of the project.

4 experimentation/demonstration sites participate in the project and are managed by public transport operators in Lyon, Geneva, Luxembourg and Copenhagen. The project being an experiment, its approach in using vehicles is rather cautious: vehicles operate at relatively low speed, on predefined routes with no or very little traffic, under the constant supervision of on-board safety drivers. Of course, this seriously limits the relevance of such vehicles, both in economic and quality of services terms. To demonstrate any relevance, their flexibility would need to improve (on-demand service), they should be able to use existing infrastructure and share it with other road users, they should operate at higher speed, and they should not depend on on-board personnel. This of course poses many safety challenges: interactions with other actors will become more complex; the environment might be less known and predictable; while higher speeds reduce the acceptable range for reaction times and make collisions potentially fatal.

Successful deployment therefore relies on proper safety assessment of such vehicles, which was addressed by a specific work package in AVENUE. The methodology for such assessment is the focus of this paper.

Objectives

Safety assessment may encompass many dimensions, such as, e.g.:

- Functional Safety: prevent system failure resulting in injury;
- Crashworthiness: protect occupants from crashes;
- Operational Safety: e.g. avoid hurting passengers with automatic doors;
- Non-collision Safety: e.g. avoid exposing passengers or personnel to electrical hazard;
- **Safety Of The Intended Functionality [1]: i.e. properly handle situations met on open road.**

Among these challenges, the last one is the most *specific* to automated minibuses. With nobody behind the wheel, proper situational awareness and swift response to danger are crucial to ensure safety. It also is the most *complex* challenge, as it not only depends on the vehicle's own characteristics (which ultimately are the manufacturer's own responsibility), but also on *how* and *where* it is used.

It was therefore decided to focus AVENUE's effort on this topic, developing a methodology practical and generic enough to be used in future projects.

Using feedback from the field tests, description of future plans, and a mix of simulation and physical testing, such methodology was developed. It relies on:

- Identifying situations which might cause safety problems when the operational design domain of the shuttles is extended.
- For those situations, expose the *relationship between vehicle capabilities and the situations* that can safely be addressed (e.g. which speed can be attained using current vehicle technology in a pedestrian-dense environment; which change in vehicle capability needs to be implemented before using the shuttle in mixed traffic...)

Our approach was to rely on previous work (from partners & literature) when relevant, but also identify specificities of automated minibuses and resulting gaps, then use state-of-the-art methods and

tools to assess the impact of said gaps.

For instance, protecting vulnerable road users outside of a traditional passenger car doesn't present much dilemma: the vehicle's occupants are properly sat and restrained; there are little reasons not to brake decisively when risking hitting a much less protected traffic participant (e.g. pedestrian). This is not the case for a minibus where passengers might be standing unrestrained: a harsh braking might result in a passenger freefalling, leading to serious injuries or worse. A **trade-off** between passenger and external vulnerable road users' safety seems inevitable. Moreover, while a passenger car's driver might be impaired or distracted in a way a robot never will, he/she can conversely conceptualise interactions and anticipate other traffic participants' intents, relying on past experience and non-verbal interactions (e.g. exchanging glances), in a way that a robot cannot. Such example illustrates specificities of such vehicles, which had to be addressed by an extensive injury risk study for both passengers and vulnerable road users, and simulations of complex interactions with external traffic participants.

Methodology

The methodology relies on several steps, as described on Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 – Methodology overview

- The first step consists in identifying hazards, in the form of relevant scenarios. As automated minibuses follow a predefined path at a predefined speed, we defined relevant scenarios as *any circumstances which mandated significant alteration of either path or speed (e.g. braking) to avoid a collision*. A scenario catalogue was constituted, based on pre-existing knowledge on urban accident scenarios, examination of test sites' infrastructure to deduce possibly problematic interactions, and operator feedbacks during interviews and a focus group. It was then ranked / prioritised by the operators and their safety drivers using an innovative

approach described further below.

- The second step consists in quantifying those hazards. This step allows giving a weight -a probability- for each scenario to be met, not only in broad terms (occurrence of a scenario of a certain category, i.e. a *functional scenario* as per [2]), but also taking into account the parameters describing it which might have an impact on the outcome. Such parameters as initial speeds, relative positions etc. are summarised in the form of multivariate distributions. This relies on detailed sensor data collection and processing, which is also further described below.
- The third step consists in assessing how the vehicle would handle each possible situation (i.e. each parameters' tuple), depending on its own characteristics (e.g. sensors location) relying on massive simulations. Behaviour of the automated minibus is simulated in a virtual environment, which provides kinematics (positions and speeds for the minibus and other relevant traffic participants). Parameters which impact the vehicle's behaviour, such as sensors' type and position, can safely be explored through that approach.
- The final step consists in estimating actual risk, by computing performance indicators for passengers and other traffic participants' safety. This requires injury risk models which take the relevant kinematics parameters as inputs: relative speed and position at collision for vulnerable road users; braking characteristics for passengers. An injury risk study was carried out to develop such injury risk models.

Figure 2 below summarises how, for one specific scenario, data collection and processing, injury risk models and simulations contribute to estimating the associated risk. Each step is further described in subsequent sections.

Figure 2 – Application of the methodology to one scenario

Identifying and ranking relevant scenarios

As previously exposed, a preliminary analysis resulted in the identification and description of potentially problematic scenarios, in the form of a collection of 189 functional scenarios. The next planned step was to organise focus groups with safety drivers with the hope to identify potentially overlooked scenarios, rank the existing ones by criticality and in a more general way identify current roadblocks towards higher speeds and remote monitoring. The topics addressed in the focus group methodology were:

- **General attitude of safety drivers in relation with their mission** (*does safety naturally emerge as the main concern?*). Safety drivers were asked about how they describe their own job to their friends, which were their biggest surprise when starting this job, what they feel is the most important part of their job, what kind of difficulty they encounter...
- **Safety**. Safety drivers were asked whether they felt concerned about overall safety and whether they felt specifically concerned about passengers' safety or other traffic participants' safety. Interventions they had to perform in order to preserve safety and their circumstances were also discussed.
- **Higher operation speed**. The path to a higher speed and potential roadblocks to reach this goal were discussed.
- **Replacing safety drivers with remote monitoring** was finally discussed in a similar way.

The focus group was then followed by a discussion around scenarios, to identify those they find most concerning.

Unfortunately, only one focus group (with Lyon's safety drivers) could be carried out, before Covid-19 related lockdowns prevented such activities. Safety drivers in Lyon considered that the vehicle behaviour generally was appropriate. However, the vehicle, in its development stage at the time, imposed frequent harsh braking and could not overtake static obstacles, even those barely overlapping its path. Safety drivers therefore learnt to anticipate and mitigate such issues through manual takeover or by warning passengers of imminent harsh braking. This leads to habituation and overlooking issues, making it hard to determine a clear path to remote operation and higher speeds from just such subjective data. Focus groups being prevented by travel and pandemic related restrictions and ranking close to 200 scenarios without some kind of assistance proving particularly challenging, an innovative approach was therefore adopted.

A web application was developed. It allowed, in an administration interface (Figure 3), to define and manage scenarios. On the front-end, it presented two applications (Figure 4), accessible to safety drivers and their management: one application allowed creating incident reports using an intelligent form; another application allowed scenario ranking through pair-wise comparisons between scenarios. For each pair of scenarios, the participants were encouraged to vote for the one which "seems, for them, most likely to result one day in an accident". Matches between scenarios and the ranking itself relied on the TrueSkill algorithm [3]. This allowed, through hundreds of contributions, to slowly

iterate towards a per-site ranking of scenarios (Figure 5).

Figure 3 – Scenario management interface

Figure 4 – Frontend for incident reports and scenarios ranking

Sales Lentz Autocars - Luxembourg

Keolis - Lyon - Groupama Stadium

Amobility - Copenhagen – Nordhavn

Transport Publics Genevois

Figure 5 – Most relevant / critical scenarios for each test site

These preliminary calculation steps, resulting in high level parameters describing the situation at all time in a synthetic manner, allowed detecting and characterising scenarios using simple sets of rules. Implementing them in SALSA allowed automating the complete process.

Simulating the minibus' behaviour

While the previous steps aim at characterising the reality that a minibus has to deal with, simulations allow assessing how it might handle them, depending on its own characteristics (e.g. software, sensors' type and location...).

A simulation toolchain has been set-up. It consists of a **virtual environment** (Vires VTD) where scenarios are played. Virtual sensors provide streams which can feed a **driving controller**. As the actual controller software from the minibuses used in AVENUE could not be used, a generic longitudinal and lateral controller has been developed. From this controller, commands are issued to actuators models (motor; braking) in a **dynamic model** of the vehicle (AVL VSM). This results in changes in its movement which are sent back to the virtual environment, constantly changing its perspective on its surroundings. A communication framework (AVL Model.Connect) allows all components of the toolchain to communicate seamlessly, enabling automation and hence massive simulations, where scenario parameters can span all possible values and multiple hypotheses in terms of vehicle design can be tested.

Figure 7 – Simulation toolchain architecture

Although not a perfect match for the minibus used in the project, the driving controller and dynamic model were adjusted to match recordings made with the actual vehicle both in emergency (test track data) and normal operation conditions.

Building injury risk models

As scenario simulations provide kinematics measures, those must be converted into key performance indicators for both passengers' and other traffic participants' (notably, vulnerable road users) safety. An **injury risk study**, relying on an extensive literature review and numerical finite-element simulations has been carried out. It aimed at providing relevant but also practical criteria for injury risk as a function of dynamic measures (e.g. deceleration profile, speed at collision). The effort was concentrated on standing passengers and pedestrians as a first step, and, as in both cases literature shows that head injuries generally are the most critical, the focus was further narrowed down to head injury risk.

For standing passengers, the injury risk is the combination of the risk of losing balance and falling, and the risk of hurting oneself when falling. To estimate the latter, numerical simulations were performed in a two steps approach: a rigid dummy model was used to study freefall while braking, providing the head speed at contact; deformable models were then used to study impact between the head and a handling bar, providing head acceleration. From head acceleration, Head Injury Criterion (HIC) [4] and hence, risk of skull fracture could be deduced. Simulations showed that HIC could easily reach very high values in case of a freefall: it therefore is critical to make sure that passengers won't ever lose their balance. Robert & Vallée [5] quantified the effects of the jerk and the force on the balance recovery for a young population, in an experimental setup where those sustained a controlled pulse being applied to their waist, while being asked to try not to step in response. The discomfort caused by the perturbation was evaluated by the volunteers and results were aggregated through a multivariate logistic regression into a simple function of jerk and acceleration. This provided a practical indicator which was used for passenger's related risk.

For pedestrians, given the vertical shape of the vehicle's frontend, and the presence of protruding sensors, it was assumed that risk curves deduced from accident research [6] would not apply. Numerical simulations therefore were performed (Figure 8). A numerical model of the vehicle's frontend was developed and used with dummy and human body models, with various relative positions and impact speeds, to produce skull fracture risk curves as a function of impact speed. For pedestrian related risk, two key performance indicators were finally used: the minimum distance between the pedestrian and the vehicle, and the risk of skull fracture in case of contact.

Figure 8 – Pedestrians / minibus collision simulations

Conclusion

A methodology has been developed, and the corresponding tools have been implemented, resulting in a **practical toolchain** that can be used to assess safety of automated minibus in a virtual environment. This methodology relies on actual data, collected from test sites, to characterise the operating environment in terms of a succession of scenarios, defined by their parameters. This results in a virtual representation of the challenges that an automated urban vehicle has to address, which can then be used in numerical simulations. Key performance indicators, to assess the criticality of each individual simulation run have been selected and/or developed.

This methodology has been applied to select scenarios, based on their perceived criticality. Thanks to the aforementioned toolchain, it could be used at a much higher scale, to result in a comprehensive and prospective (e.g. taking into account future vehicle development or new operating speed) risk assessment.

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